

Supplementary information: Using mixed fidelity simulation to maximise basic laparoscopic skills training and self-confidence

Supplementary Table 1. Pre-course survey

Question	Answer
What is your current grade?	Medical Student FY1 doctor CST1 CST2 Trust grade/junior clinical fellow Other
What is your experience with simulation training for surgical skills?	No experience Basic surgical skills simulation (suturing on skin pad, BSS course) Laparoscopic box simulator Laparoscopic wet lab simulation Augmented reality simulation (laparoscopy) Augmented reality simulation (other) Virtual reality simulation (laparoscopy) Virtual reality (other) ALSGBI lapPass course
What is your level of theatre experience? (not specific to laparoscopy)	Never been in theatre Observed in theatre Assisted in <10 cases Assisted in >10 cases Performed with supervision <10 cases Performed with supervision >10 cases Performed cases without supervision
What is your level of theatre experience? (specific to laparoscopy)	Never been in theatre Observed in theatre Assisted in <10 cases Assisted in >10 cases Performed with supervision <10 cases Performed with supervision >10 cases Performed cases without supervision
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Principles of laparoscopy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Assisting in laparoscopic surgery	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Basic laparoscopic skill tasks	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Access and induction of pneumoperitoneum	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident

How would you rate your level of confidence in: Laparoscopic suturing	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Use of electro-cautery in laparoscopy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Use of energy devices in laparoscopy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: uncomplicated appendicectomy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: difficult appendicectomy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: cholecystectomy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident

Supplementary Table 2. Immediate post-course survey

Question	Answer
What is your current grade?	Medical Student FY1 doctor CST1 CST2 Trust grade/junior clinical fellow Other
What is your experience with simulation training for surgical skills?	No experience Basic surgical skills simulation (suturing on skin pad, BSS course) Laparoscopic box simulator Laparoscopic wet lab simulation Augmented reality simulation (laparoscopy) Augmented reality simulation (other) Virtual reality simulation (laparoscopy) Virtual reality (other) ALSGBI lapPass course
What is your level of theatre experience? (not specific to laparoscopy)	Never been in theatre Observed in theatre Assisted in <10 cases Assisted in >10 cases Performed with supervision <10 cases Performed with supervision >10 cases Performed cases without supervision
What is your level of theatre experience? (specific to laparoscopy)	Never been in theatre Observed in theatre Assisted in <10 cases Assisted in >10 cases Performed with supervision <10 cases Performed with supervision >10 cases Performed cases without supervision
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Principles of laparoscopy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Assisting in laparoscopic surgery	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Basic laparoscopic skill tasks	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Access and induction of pneumoperitoneum	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Laparoscopic suturing	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident

How would you rate your level of confidence in: Use of electro-cautery in laparoscopy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Use of energy devices in laparoscopy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: uncomplicated appendicectomy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: difficult appendicectomy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: cholecystectomy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident

Supplementary Table 3. Two-month post-course survey

Question	Answer
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Principles of laparoscopy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Assisting in laparoscopic surgery	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Basic laparoscopic skill tasks	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Access and induction of pneumoperitoneum	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Laparoscopic suturing	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Use of electro-cautery in laparoscopy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Use of energy devices in laparoscopy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: uncomplicated appendicectomy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: difficult appendicectomy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
How would you rate your level of confidence in: cholecystectomy	Likert scale 1 – 10 Not at all confident – Very confident
Have you had a chance to use your skills in theatre?	Yes/No

Supplementary Table 4. Two-month post-course survey results

Question	Mean score (standard deviation)
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Principles of laparoscopy	8.3 (1.03)
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Assisting in laparoscopic surgery	8.6 (1.37)
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Basic laparoscopic skill tasks	8.3 (1.49)
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Access and induction of pneumoperitoneum	7.2 (2.27)
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Laparoscopic suturing	7.7 (1.25)
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Use of electro-cautery in laparoscopy	7.7 (1.37)
How would you rate your level of confidence in: Use of energy devices in laparoscopy	7.7 (1.37)
How would you rate your level of confidence in: uncomplicated appendicectomy	7.5 (1.61)
How would you rate your level of confidence in: difficult appendicectomy	6 (2.38)
How would you rate your level of confidence in: cholecystectomy	6.78 (1.77)
Have you had a chance to use your skills in theatre?	83% Yes